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Enhancing the Reading Comprehension Skills of Grade 4 Frustrated Readers Through the Passages of Araling Panlipunan Competencies

JELYNE M. ESTRELLA, MAEd

Master Teacher 1

Karangalan Elementary School

Rizal Province

Abstract

The study aims to enhance the reading comprehension skills of Grade 4 frustrated readers by integrating passages from Araling Panlipunan competencies. Addressing the specific challenges faced by these students is crucial, as improving reading comprehension is foundational for their academic success across all subjects. By utilizing content from Araling Panlipunan, the study provides a dual-focus approach, allowing students to improve their reading skills while deepening their understanding of important historical, cultural, and social concepts. This initiative aims to develop and implement effective, evidence-based interventions tailored to the needs of frustrated readers, which can be integrated into regular teaching practices. Enhancing these skills at an early age not only boosts academic performance but also fosters a love for reading and lifelong learning, promoting long-term educational and personal growth. The participants of the study are the Grade 4 learners who were identified as frustrated readers based on the September 2023 Phil-IRI assessment in Filipino. The study was conducted on the 2nd quarter of school year 2023-2024 at Karangalan Elementary School in Cainta, Rizal. Based on the findings of the study, the data from multiple assessments and interventions indicates a substantial improvement in student performance across various metrics. The positive trend in average grades, observed through consistent increases, suggests that the teaching methods or interventions applied were highly effective in enhancing student understanding and performance. Specifically, the transition from 100% of students being at the Non-Mastery Level to all students achieving either Nearing Mastery or Mastery Levels demonstrates the profound impact of targeted educational strategies on learning outcomes. The results from these interventions highlight the potential of well-implemented educational approaches to dramatically improve academic performance. The significant rise in mean grades between quarters, coupled with strong statistical evidence, confirms the effectiveness of these strategies. Such findings advocate for the continuation and possible expansion of these interventions to maintain and further enhance student success. Reflecting on these findings, the interventions were not only successful in raising

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student performance but also in providing a model for future educational practices. The consistent improvement across different assessments underscores the importance of targeted, well-designed teaching methods. These results suggest that similar strategies could be applied in various educational contexts to achieve significant improvements, emphasizing the critical role of effective interventions in fostering academic excellence and mastery of subject matter.

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